

**Job-Related Training and Planned Retirement Age in Germany:
Evidence from the German Ageing Survey (DEAS)**

Schmelzle, Rebecca
Henning, Georg

German Centre of Gerontology, Berlin, Germany

Abstract

Population ageing increases the importance of understanding factors that shape planned retirement age. Job-related training may influence retirement planning by enhancing human capital and employability while fostering reciprocal employment relationships. Empirical evidence on this relationship remains limited, particularly for Germany. Using data from the German Ageing Survey (DEAS) 2020/21 and 2023, this study examines whether participation in job-related training is associated with planned retirement age and changes in planned retirement age over time. We used cross-sectional linear regressions to estimate associations of job-related training participation with planned retirement age, as well as fixed-effects panel models to test whether training participation between waves was linked to within-person increases in planned retirement age. The results show little evidence of a general association training participation and planned retirement age. However, longitudinal analyses suggest a positive association between training participation and an increase in planned retirement age for individuals aged 55 to 59. Overall, our findings suggest that the relationship between lifelong learning and retirement planning is context-dependent and may be particularly relevant during specific phases of the late career.

Keywords: Planned retirement age; Job-related training; Lifelong learning; Older workers

Correspondence: Rebecca Schmelzle, German Centre of Gerontology, Manfred-von-Richthofen-Straße 2, 12101 Berlin, Germany. Email: Rebecca.schmelzle@dza.de

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Data Availability Statement

The data underlying this article were provided by the German Centre of Gerontology (DZA) by permission. The data can be requested via the following link:
<https://www.dza.de/en/research/fdz/german-ageing-survey/access-to-deas-data>

Introduction

In light of the ageing work force and declining birth rates, many governments around the world are implementing policies to increase the labour market participation of older workers (Hofäcker et al., 2016). In Germany, the traditional “early exit” culture has been gradually replaced since the 1990s by policies implemented by successive governments encouraging longer work lives (Hess, 2016). The statutory retirement age is currently raised stepwise from 65 (until the birth cohort of 1947) to 67 for birth cohorts from 1964 on, and several rules allowing earlier retirement for special groups have been abandoned. Nevertheless, under certain circumstances, earlier retirement is still possible, though often only when accepting pension cuts. Although the actual retirement age is rising and the labour market participation of older workers is increasing, the average effective retirement age remains below the statutory retirement age (Bundesinstitut für Bevölkerungsforschung, 2024) and the average duration of pension benefit receipt is increasing (Statistisches Bundesamt (Destatis), 2026).

This is not only a burden for the pension system, but also a problem for companies who do not find personnel to replace the retirees. Moreover, a longer working life is also discussed as a potential aid for healthy aging, because of important cognitive, social and physical activity at the workplace if the working conditions are adequate (Staudinger et al., 2016) and because of the financial incentives for adaptive health behaviour existing for those working, but not those retired (Mazzonna & Perracchi, 2012).

Therefore, it is an important political and societal question how to prolong the individual working life. One potential factor is job-related training, potentially helping the worker to remain up-to-date with current developments (Hennekam, 2015) and to foster a feeling of reciprocity for the employer (de Grip et al., 2020), facilitating a longer

working life. In the present paper, we investigate the association of job-related training and planned retirement age.

Background

Job-related training and planned retirement age

Individual retirement timing is complex and has a multifactorial genesis: If and when people retire depends on the individual ability (health, skills, availability of jobs, etc.) and individual desire (financial aspects, enjoying work, etc.) to continue working (de Wind et al., 2015). Retirement timing is shaped by multiple individual, work-related, family-related and macroeconomic factors (Fisher et al., 2016).

Previous research indicates that job-related training is associated with improved performance, higher work motivation and lower turnover intentions (de Grip & Sauermann, 2013; Hansson, 2009; Dysvik & Kuvaas, 2008). In light of the greying workforce, job-related training has also been seen as a potential means to achieve longer working lives and later retirement. First, job-related training enables workers to update their skills so they can continue meeting changing job requirements (Gruenewald & Mueller, 2025). However, various theories also suggest a possible effect via motivational changes.

To explain why the willingness to work longer after training participation could be a rational choice, human capital theory understands training participation as an investment in workers' human capital, as it enhances skills and productivity accumulated over the life course. Because such investments are assumed to generate future returns, they may therefore contribute to extending working lives in order to recoup these investments (Becker, 1964; Ben-Porath, 1967).

Furthermore, employer-provided training may influence retirement planning beyond skill acquisition: The motivated choice framework suggests that workers are more likely to continue working when their development needs are met and they perceive their work environment as supportive (Kanfer et al., 2013), suggesting that job-related training may be linked to later retirement planning. Consequently, Li et al. (2023) showed that the effect of training on the intention to retire was mediated by increased perceived person-organization fit and needs-supply fit.

Reciprocity theory, embedded in Social Exchange Theory (Cropanzano & Mitchell, 2011), argues from the perspective of the worker-employer relationship: an investment, especially in older workers, despite existing stereotypes regarding their performance (Posthuma & Campion, 2009), may cause a feeling of obligation to reciprocate (Gouldner, 1960). Thus, participating in training activities may foster a feeling of reciprocity for the employer, increasing the willingness to remain employed longer (de Grip et al., 2020).

Finally, the intention to retire can be influenced by perceived negative age stereotypes (Dordoni et al., 2017). Such stereotypes – e.g. assumptions of lower ability, motivation, and productivity – may also be internalized by older workers themselves and thereby shape their decision-making (Posthuma & Campion, 2009). In this context, the performance-enhancing and motivational effects of training participation may partly counteract these stereotypes of older workers.

The moderating role of age

When examining the association between job-related training participation and planned retirement age, it is important to consider the potentially moderating role of age. Previous research has revealed that managers are less likely to offer training to older workers than to younger workers (Karpinska et al., 2015), and that older workers

themselves tend to be less interested in training participation (Ng et al. 2010). From an economic perspective, this may reflect a rational decision, as the remaining time to recoup investments in new skills is shorter in late career stages (Mayhew et al., 2008). In line with this, research on lifespan changes in work motives suggests that the importance of growth-related motives declines over the course of working life (Kooij et al., 2011), implying that job-related training may become less strongly linked to planned retirement age with increasing age. Instead, other factors – such as relationships with co-workers – may become more important, reflecting the increasing relevance of intrinsic work motives in later life (Kooij et al., 2011). Nevertheless, these patterns may also be influenced by managers' as well as internalized age stereotypes at work (Posthuma & Campion, 2009), which can shape both the provision of and engagement in training opportunities.

As retirement decision-making is a longitudinal multi-phase process, the planned retirement age is likely to have a different meaning at different stages of the career lifespan. Feldman and Beehr (2011) argue that retirement decision-making includes three main steps – imagining the possibility of retiring, assessing the right time to retire, and finally developing and following concrete plans for retirement. Younger workers are likely to have a less concrete view of their retirement process and job-related training may therefore have less influence than later in the work life. The most crucial time point for effects of job-related training may be when people start to assess their skills and the job-environment fit. Very late in one's working life, when work disengagement processes in preparation of retirement have already set in (Henning et al., 2023; 2026; Super, 1980), it is less likely to influence retirement plans. Respectively, also the impact of career development opportunities on employee engagement is only salient for workers who have not reached retirement-eligible age

yet (Boone James et al., 2011). These considerations imply that age as a moderator may follow a u-shaped pattern, with weaker associations of job-related training and planned retirement age in younger and older workers and the strongest association sometime in midlife, potentially in one's 50s, when retirement plans are getting more concrete but are not set in stone yet.

State of the art

Empirical research on the association of job-related training and actual retirement is limited and shows mixed results. Kristensen (2012) found only small effects of publicly funded training on retirement age in Denmark, whereas a study by Stenberg and Westerlund (2013) suggested that university education in midlife was associated with longer working lives and estimated the effects as rather large in Sweden. Nägele et al. (2025), using three waves of the same dataset we use in our analyses, the German Ageing Survey, found that those workers aged 46-75 at baseline who reported more job-related training in the waves 2014 and 2017 were more likely to still be in employment in 2021. Investigating the macro-level, Mäcken and colleagues (2022) showed that the country-level participation rate in lifelong learning activities was associated with less social inequalities in the retirement age, but effects were small as well.

Associations of job-related training with planned or intended retirement age have rarely been investigated. Stynen et al. (2016) found an association between development practices and later retirement intentions among older workers in Denmark, but no isolated association between training participation and early retirement preferences. Seeberg et al. (2025) investigated the association between skill development and expected retirement age among state employees in Denmark and found a positive, robust association between skill development through formal

education and expected retirement age. Mok et al. (2023) found a positive association between work training and skill development and the expected retirement age among injured older workers (45 and above) in Australia.

Instead of actual individual training participation, some studies have also focused on the impact of offering training opportunities in general. Herrbach et al. (2009) found that training opportunities were associated with a lower likelihood of retiring across 30 months, whereas van Solinge and Henkens (2014) found no such association for retirement timing. De Grip et al. (2020) reported that training opportunities were associated with expected retirement age over and beyond actual participation in training, but with an effect only for workers that hold strong positive reciprocity beliefs. Dordoni et al. (2017) found a negative association between perceived job support for learning and the intention to retire.

One possible reason for the mixed findings are differences in national contexts as well as in how training (e.g., publicly funded only or general opportunities instead of actual training participation) and retirement outcomes (e.g., intended, planned, or actual retirement) are specified. Here, we focus on retirement intentions and more specifically, planned retirement age. Planned retirement age predicts actual retirement age relatively well (Engstler, 2019; Ilmakunnas & Ilmakunnas, 2018). However, retirement plans and actual retirement timing can mis-match, either by unexpectedly working or by unexpectedly not working. Deviations between planned retirement and actual retirement differ systematically per minority race, education level and birth cohort (Abrams et al., 2022) and can be influenced by unexpected events such as health shocks (Ilmakunnas & Ilmakunnas, 2018). Retirement planning reflects a combination of preferences, normative expectations, and perceived opportunities; it can be understood as a pragmatic interface between personal preferences and (not

least financial) realities, and is contingent upon further factors such as health and work capacity, whose future trajectories are not always foreseeable (Hasselhorn & Borchart, 2025). Examining planned retirement age allows identifying how job-related training shapes retirement planning across individuals of all ages, and to also capture within-person change over time.

The present study

In the present study, we used two waves of the German Ageing Survey (Klaus et al., 2017; Vogel et al., 2022) to investigate the association of job-related training and planned retirement age. We focus both on cross-sectional associations in 2023 as well as on longitudinal associations between 2020/21 and 2023. Based on the literature and theories presented above, we assume:

H1: Employed individuals who participate in job-related training report a higher planned retirement age.

H1a: The association between participation in job-related training and planned retirement age differs by age group.

H2: Participation in job-related training is associated with an increase in planned retirement age over time.

H2a: The association between participation in job-related training and increases in the planned retirement age differs by age group.

It is important to note that possible associations of training participation and planned retirement age can have different explanations. Apart from a causal effect of training participation, it may also be retirement plans that influence if someone participates in training, or that third variables, for example performance at the

workplace or specific health issues that we do not assess in our dataset, influence who is offered training or can participate in it.

Data & Methods

Sample

The current study is based on two waves of data (2020/21 and 2023) from the German Ageing Survey (DEAS) (Klaus et al., 2017; Vogel et al., 2022). The DEAS is a population-based longitudinal multi-cohort study of the second half of life. In 1996, 2002, 2008 and 2014, four baseline samples of the German population aged 40-80 were drawn from the population registry and the resulting study samples were reinterviewed at every new wave, with additional panel interviews in 2011, 2017, summer 2020 (short survey during the covid pandemic), winter 2020/2021 and 2023. We restricted the sample to respondents who were employed in 2023 (H1, H1a) as well as in 2020/21 (H2, H2a) aged 43 to 65 in 2023. Respondents whose planned retirement age was below their current age were excluded due to logical implausibility. We also excluded those reporting a planned retirement age of 80 years and older, as we considered these values unrealistic given typical retirement patterns and treated them as outliers. Respondents working as contributing family members or in the military were also excluded, as these groups could not be consistently classified within the occupational categories and represented only a very small number of cases.

Analyses are based on $n = 1,133$ (H1, H1a) and $n = 704$ (H2, H2a) participants.

Measures

Job-related training. Job-related training was assessed by the question: "There are courses and advanced occupational training programs available for many

occupations. Think back over the past 3 years. Did you attend any training, courses, seminars, or events to provide occupational training or vocational retraining?" with answer alternatives yes or no (1/0).

Planned retirement age. We used information on the planned age of work exit. Workers were asked: "At what age do you plan to stop working?". 14.9% (n = 220) did not provide an answer to the question ("don't know").

Changes in planned retirement. For the longitudinal analyses, we focused on within-individual changes in planned retirement age between 2020/21 and 2023. Accordingly, the dependent variable captures the change in planned retirement age across the two waves.

Control variables. We controlled the cross-sectional analyses for several factors that may influence both the participation in job-related training and planned retirement age. Following Fisher et al. (2016), we included individual, work-related, and family-related antecedents. At the individual level, we controlled for gender (0 = men, 1 = women), as men are more likely to work up to or beyond retirement age (Hofäcker & Naumann, 2015). We further accounted for age, as older workers are generally less likely to participate in job-related training than younger workers (Henning et al., 2025) and are also more likely to plan a later retirement, partly due to selection effects - whereby those still employed at older ages are more likely to continue working than others from their birth cohort - partly because statutory retirement ages differ across birth cohorts, and as planned retirement age cannot be reported below one's current age. Following Stynen et al. (2016), we distinguish three age groups: prime age workers (≤ 54 years), individuals approaching retirement (55-59 years), and those anticipating retirement (60-65 years). We further controlled for

educational attainment. Education was included as higher-educated individuals tend to both participate more frequently in training and remain in the labor force longer (Henning et al., 2025; Hofäcker et al., 2016). We used the ISCED classification available in the DEAS SUF data file and distinguished between high (1) and middle/low educational attainment (0). Additionally, we controlled for region (0 = Western Germany, 1 = Eastern Germany). We further included job-related characteristics: First, given that retirement decisions are often made at the household level (Fisher et al. 2016), we added equivalized net household income. Based on data from the European Union Statistics on Income and Living Conditions, we categorized income into three groups: (0) low income (below 60% of the median), (1) medium income (60-150% of the median), and (2) high income (above 150% of the median). For 2023, the median monthly income was €2,190, resulting in a threshold of €1,314 (60%) and €3,284 (150%). We further included occupational category (0 = high-skilled white-collar, 1 = low-skilled white-collar, 2 = high-skilled blue-collar, 3 = low-skilled blue-collar); the sector (0 = production sector (agriculture, industry, crafts), 1 = private trade and service sector, 2 = public sector), and working hours (0 = full time (\geq 35 hours/ week), 1 = part-time ($<$ 35 hours/ week)). We also controlled for functional limitations (0 = no, 1 = yes) and marital status (0 = not married, 1 = married). Finally, in line with Kaboth & Meyer (2026), work-related stressors were included, capturing physical activities, environmental factors, high workload, and new demands (0 = not/ hardly/ a bit stressed, 1 = (very) stressed).

Analyses

To test hypothesis 1 and 1a, we estimated linear regression models with increasing levels of adjustments. Model 1 included only participation in job-related training. Model 2 additionally controlled for demographic characteristics, while Model

3 further incorporated education and region. In Model 4, job-related characteristics were added. Model 5 additionally accounted for marital status and functional limitations, and Model 6 included indicators of work-related stressors. Finally, Model 7 introduced an interaction between age group and participation in job-related training to examine whether the association varies across different stages of late working life. All analyses apply survey weights and account for the complex stratified and clustered sampling design of the DEAS.

To test hypothesis 2 and 2a, we estimated linear fixed-effects regression models using panel data from 2020/21 and 2023. The dependent variable captured the change in planned retirement age between the two waves. The key independent variable was participation in job-related training measured at the 2023 wave, reflecting training activities between 2020/21 and 2023. To assess whether associations differ across stages of late working life, we included interactions between training participation and baseline age group (based on 2020/21). Control variables largely mirrored those used in the cross-sectional analyses, namely household income, occupational category, sector, working hours, marital status, functional limitations, and work-related stressors. Additionally, we controlled for external health shocks occurring between 2020/21 and 2023 (measured at the 2023 wave), capturing if respondents have experienced a serious illness and/or an accident within the past 3 years (1 = yes) or not (0 = no). All models were estimated using individual fixed effects to account for unobserved time-invariant heterogeneity, thus not including time-invariant characteristics. We applied the corresponding longitudinal weights to account for panel attrition and sampling design for the longitudinal analyses.

Results

Cross-sectional associations between job-related training and planned retirement age

Sample description. Sample description for the 2023 wave, stratified by age group, are presented in Table 1 (unweighted) and Table 2 (weighted).

Table 1

Descriptive Sample 2023 by Age Group, Unweighted

	43-54 years N = 362 (32.0%)	55-59 years N = 364 (32.1%)	60-65 years N = 407 (35.9%)	Total sample N = 1,133
Planned retirement age Mean (SD)	64.33 (3.29)	64.54 (2.46)	64.93 (1.69)	64.61 (2.55)
Job-related training				
No	92 (25.4%)	145 (39.8%)	193 (47.4%)	430 (38.0%)
Yes	270 (74.6%)	219 (60.2%)	214 (52.6%)	703 (62.0%)
Gender				
Male	158 (43.6%)	169 (46.4%)	201 (49.4%)	528 (46.6%)
Female	204 (56.4%)	195 (53.6%)	206 (50.6%)	605 (53.4%)
Educational attainment (ISCED)				
Low/medium	158 (43.6%)	197 (54.1%)	184 (45.2%)	539 (47.6%)
High	204 (56.4%)	167 (45.9%)	223 (54.8%)	594 (52.4%)
Region				
Western Germany	255 (70.4%)	251 (69.0%)	288 (70.8%)	794 (70.1%)
Eastern Germany	107 (29.6%)	113 (31.0%)	119 (29.2%)	339 (29.9%)
Income				
Low	17 (4.7%)	16 (4.4%)	20 (4.9%)	53 (4.7%)
Medium	256 (70.7%)	233 (64.0%)	261 (64.1%)	750 (66.2%)
High	89 (24.6%)	115 (31.6%)	126 (31.0%)	330 (29.1%)
Occupational category				
High skilled white collar	255 (70.4%)	222 (61.0%)	268 (65.8%)	745 (65.8%)

Low skilled white collar	55 (15.2%)	65 (17.9%)	63 (15.5%)	183 (16.2%)
High skilled blue collar	30 (8.3%)	36 (9.9%)	37 (9.1%)	103 (9.1%)
Low skilled blue collar	22 (6.1%)	41 (11.3%)	39 (9.6%)	102 (9.0%)
Sector				
Production sector (agriculture, industry, crafts)	97 (26.8%)	91 (25.0%)	109 (26.8%)	297 (26.2%)
Private trade and service sector	151 (41.7%)	138 (37.9%)	163 (40.0%)	452 (39.9%)
Public sector	114 (31.5%)	135 (37.1%)	135 (33.2%)	384 (33.9%)
Weekly working hours				
Full-time (>=35h/week)	259 (71.5%)	266 (73.1%)	299 (73.5%)	824 (72.7%)
Part-time (<35h/week)	103 (28.5%)	98 (26.9%)	108 (26.5%)	309 (27.3%)
Marital status				
Not married	115 (31.8%)	98 (26.9%)	113 (27.8%)	326 (28.8%)
Married	247 (68.2%)	266 (73.1%)	294 (72.2%)	807 (71.2%)
Functional impairments				
No	274 (75.7%)	263 (72.3%)	297 (73.0%)	834 (73.6%)
Yes	88 (24.3%)	101 (27.7%)	110 (27.0%)	299 (26.4%)
Work stress: Physical activities				
Not/hardly/a bit stressed	271 (74.9%)	279 (76.6%)	298 (73.2%)	848 (74.8%)
(Very) stressed	91 (25.1%)	85 (23.4%)	109 (26.8%)	285 (25.2%)
Work stress: Environmental factors				
Not/hardly/a bit stressed	319 (88.1%)	322 (88.5%)	347 (85.3%)	988 (87.2%)
(Very) stressed	43 (11.9%)	42 (11.5%)	60 (14.7%)	145 (12.8%)
Work stress: High workload				
Not/hardly/a bit stressed	203 (56.1%)	218 (59.9%)	261 (64.1%)	682 (60.2%)
(Very) stressed	159 (43.9%)	146 (40.1%)	146 (35.9%)	451 (39.8%)
Work stress: New demands				
Not/hardly/a bit stressed	283 (78.2%)	276 (75.8%)	306 (75.2%)	865 (76.3%)
(Very) stressed	79 (21.8%)	88 (24.2%)	101 (24.8%)	268 (23.7%)

Table 2

Descriptive Sample 2023 by Age Group, Weighted

	43-54 years N = 794 (45.2%)	55-59 years N = 567 (32.2%)	60-65 years N = 397 (22.6%)	Total sample N = 1,758
Planned retirement age <i>Mean (SD)</i>	64.26 (3.40)	64.59 (2.33)	65.09 (1.70)	64.56 (2.78)
Job-related training				
No	214 (26.9%)	252 (44.5%)	200 (50.3%)	666 (37.9%)
Yes	580 (73.1%)	315 (55.5%)	198 (49.7%)	1,093 (62.1%)
Gender				
Male	397 (50.0%)	304 (53.6%)	210 (52.8%)	911 (51.8%)
Female	397 (50.0%)	263 (46.4%)	187 (47.2%)	848 (48.2%)
Educational attainment (ISCED)				
Low/medium	408 (51.4%)	366 (64.5%)	238 (59.9%)	1,012 (57.6%)
High	386 (48.6%)	201 (35.5%)	159 (40.1%)	746 (42.4%)
Region				
Western Germany	660 (83.1%)	458 (80.8%)	333 (83.9%)	1,452 (82.6%)
Eastern Germany	134 (16.9%)	109 (19.2%)	64 (16.1%)	306 (17.4%)
Income				
Low	32 (4.0%)	52 (9.2%)	31 (7.9%)	115 (6.6%)
Medium	584 (73.5%)	377 (66.5%)	267 (67.3%)	1,228 (69.8%)
High	179 (22.5%)	138 (24.3%)	99 (24.8%)	415 (23.6%)
Occupational category				
High skilled white collar	509 (64.1%)	314 (55.4%)	226 (57.0%)	1,049 (59.7%)
Low skilled white collar	148 (18.7%)	109 (19.1%)	94 (23.6%)	350 (19.9%)
High skilled blue collar	79 (9.9%)	57 (10.1%)	31 (7.8%)	167 (9.5%)
Low skilled blue collar	58 (7.3%)	87 (15.4%)	46 (11.6%)	191 (10.9%)
Sector				
Production sector (agriculture, industry, crafts)	256 (32.2%)	147 (26.0%)	115 (29.0%)	518 (29.5%)
Private trade and service sector	310 (39.1%)	231 (40.7%)	170 (42.8%)	711 (40.4%)
Public sector	228 (28.8%)	189 (33.4%)	112 (28.2%)	529 (30.1%)
Weekly working hours				
Full-time (>=35h/week)	578 (72.8%)	430 (75.9%)	277 (69.8%)	1,286 (73.1%)
Part-time (<35h/week)	216 (27.2%)	136 (24.1%)	120 (30.2%)	472 (26.9%)

Marital status				
Not married	242 (30.5%)	180 (31.8%)	134 (33.6%)	555 (31.6%)
Married	552 (69.5%)	387 (68.2%)	264 (66.4%)	1,203 (68.4%)
Functional impairments				
No	592 (74.6%)	385 (68.0%)	261 (65.7%)	1,239 (70.5%)
Yes	202 (25.4%)	182 (32.0%)	136 (34.3%)	519 (29.5%)
Work stress: Physical activities				
Not/hardly/a bit stressed	590 (74.3%)	430 (75.9%)	303 (76.3%)	1,323 (75.3%)
(Very) stressed	204 (25.7%)	137 (24.1%)	94 (23.7%)	435 (24.7%)
Work stress: Environmental factors				
Not/hardly/a bit stressed	692 (87.1%)	494 (87.2%)	345 (86.9%)	1,531 (87.1%)
(Very) stressed	102 (12.9%)	73 (12.8%)	52 (13.1%)	227 (12.9%)
Work stress: High workload				
Not/hardly/a bit stressed	428 (53.9%)	347 (61.1%)	251 (63.1%)	1,025 (58.3%)
(Very) stressed	366 (46.1%)	220 (38.9%)	147 (36.9%)	733 (41.7%)
Work stress: New demands				
Not/hardly/a bit stressed	615 (77.4%)	433 (76.4%)	308 (77.6%)	1,356 (77.1%)
(Very) stressed	179 (22.6%)	134 (23.6%)	89 (22.4%)	402 (22.9%)

Note. Counts and percentages are weighted using survey weights.

In the following, we refer to the weighted data of Table 2. The analytical sample consisted of 45.2% respondents aged 43-54 years, 32.2% aged 55-59, and 22.6% aged 60-65. The average planned retirement age in the full sample was 64.6 years (SD = 2.78), with higher means among older respondents. 62.1% of the sample reported participation in job-related training. Training participation varied across age groups, ranging from 49.7% among respondents aged 60-65 to 73.1% among those aged 43-54. The majority in the sample had low to medium educational attainment (57.6%), medium income (69.8%), worked as high skilled white-collar workers (59.7%) and full-time (73.1%). The distribution of workers across the sectors was relatively balanced. The majority in the sample was married (68.4%) and did not have functional

limitations (70.5%). Most prevalent among the work stressors was a high workload, which applied to 41.7% of the sample.

Table 3 presents the results of the association between participation in job-related training and planned retirement age.

Table 3

Regression analyses of Job-related Training on Planned Retirement Age, 2023, Weighted

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)
	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7
Job-related training (ref: No)							
Yes	0.37 (0.23)	0.52* (0.25)	0.46 (0.26)	0.44 (0.25)	0.44 (0.24)	0.49* (0.24)	0.62 (0.53)
Age group (ref: 43-54 years)							
55-59 years		0.42 (0.29)	0.45 (0.29)	0.37 (0.28)	0.42 (0.28)	0.37 (0.27)	0.55 (0.52)
60-65 years		0.96*** (0.28)	0.96*** (0.28)	0.93*** (0.28)	0.99*** (0.28)	0.94*** (0.27)	1.05* (0.51)
Gender (ref: Male)							
Female		0.26 (0.22)	0.28 (0.21)	0.55* (0.25)	0.60* (0.28)	0.68* (0.28)	0.68* (0.28)
Educational attainment (ref: Low/medium)							
High			0.26 (0.25)	0.26 (0.28)	0.24 (0.28)	0.18 (0.29)	0.19 (0.28)
Region (ref: Western Germany)							
Eastern Germany			-0.09 (0.24)	-0.17 (0.24)	-0.23 (0.25)	-0.14 (0.26)	-0.14 (0.26)
Income (ref: Medium)							
Low				1.04 (0.57)	1.03 (0.55)	1.11* (0.54)	1.13* (0.54)
High				0.10 (0.29)	0.11 (0.29)	0.06 (0.29)	0.07 (0.29)
Occupational category (ref: High-skilled white collar)							
Low-skilled white collar				-0.10 (0.30)	-0.15 (0.29)	-0.07 (0.28)	-0.06 (0.27)
High-skilled blue collar				-0.52 (0.57)	-0.46 (0.54)	-0.40 (0.52)	-0.41 (0.52)
Low-skilled blue collar				0.34 (0.41)	0.33 (0.41)	0.43 (0.40)	0.40 (0.39)
Sector (ref: Production sector)							
Private trade and service sector				-0.17 (0.29)	-0.19 (0.29)	-0.22 (0.29)	-0.21 (0.29)
Public sector				-0.19 (0.27)	-0.24 (0.27)	-0.20 (0.27)	-0.19 (0.27)
Weekly working hours (ref: Full-time (>=35h/week))							
Part-time (<35h/week)				-0.63	-0.60	-0.72	-0.73

	(0.33)	(0.36)	(0.37)	(0.38)
Marital status (ref: Not married)				
Married		-0.23 (0.29)	-0.20 (0.29)	-0.21 (0.29)
Functional impairments (ref: No)				
Yes		-0.71** (0.26)	-0.55* (0.24)	-0.55* (0.24)
Work-related stressors (ref: Not/hardly/a bit stressed)				
Physical activities			-0.55 (0.28)	-0.54* (0.27)
Environmental factors			-0.38 (0.45)	-0.36 (0.43)
High workload			-0.27 (0.25)	-0.28 (0.26)
New demands			-0.21 (0.30)	-0.21 (0.30)
Interaction Job-related training and age group				
Job-related training: Yes × Age group: 55-59 years				-0.28 (0.64)
Job-related training: Yes × Age group: 60-65 years				-0.16 (0.63)
Observations	1,133	1,133	1,133	1,133
R-squared	0.00	0.02	0.03	0.05

Note. $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$

Across all model specifications M1 to M6, the coefficients of the association between participation in job-related training and planned retirement age remained positive and ranged from 0.37 (M1) to 0.52 years (M2). Statistical significance was observed only in Model 2 ($b = 0.52$, $SE = 0.25$, $p = 0.035$) and Model 6 ($b = 0.49$, $SE = 0.24$, $p = 0.044$). In the interaction Model (M7), the main effect of job-related training, as well as the interaction with age group, were not statistically significant.

Among the control variables, respondents aged 60-65 (all models), women (M4 to M7), and individuals with low income (M6 and M7) reported later planned retirement ages, whereas functional limitations (all models) and work stress through physical activities (M7) were associated with early retirement plans. Other covariates were not significantly associated with planned retirement age.

Sensitivity Analyses

For sensitivity analyses, we re-ran the 2023 models including training frequencies and excluding self-employed workers, and we replicated the analyses for 2020/21 and 2017 to test result consistency. When differentiating training by frequency (No training; 1-3 trainings; 4-10 trainings; 11 and more trainings), a positive association between training participation and planned retirement age (ref: no training participation) appeared only for the category of 1-3 training activities: the association was statistically significant across all Models M1 ($b = 0.66$, $SE = 0.28$, $p = 0.018$) to M6 ($b = 0.67$, $SE = 0.27$, $p = 0.013$). In contrast, higher training frequencies compared to no training participation were not significantly related to planned retirement age.

Excluding self-employed workers led to a substantial attenuation of the association between training participation and planned retirement age; coefficients were approximately half as large and no longer statistically significant in any model specification. In 2020/21, the association between training participation and planned retirement age was negative and not statistically significant across model specifications. Interaction analyses in 2020/21 indicated age differences: while training participation was unrelated to planned retirement age among the reference group of younger workers aged 43-54 ($b = -0.93$, $SE = 0.55$, $p = 0.094$) a positive interaction term emerged among workers aged 60-65 ($b = 1.53$, $SE = 0.51$, $p = 0.003$). In 2017, no meaningful association between training participation and planned retirement age was observed across all model specifications, and the association did not vary significantly across age groups. Moreover, the associations of control variables with planned retirement age varied strongly across years.

Fixed-Effects Analyses of Changes in Planned Retirement Age

Changes in planned retirement age between 2020/21 and 2023 are displayed in Table 4.

Table 4
Change in Planned Retirement Age (2020/21-2023) by Age Group, Weighted

Change in planned retirement age	46-54 years N = 244	55-59 years N = 327	60-63 years N = 133	Total sample N = 704
Decrease (%)	26.21	17.86	18.34	22.08
No change (%)	49.13	49.34	43.18	48.44
Increase (%)	24.66	32.80	38.49	29.48
Mean (Δ years)	-0.18	0.38	0.11	0.06
SD	1.89	1.80	1.81	1.97

Note. Age groups are based on respondents’ age in 2020/21.

Planned retirement age remained stable for nearly half of the sample (48.36%), while changes were more often towards an increase of the planned retirement age. 29.48% of all respondents increased their planned retirement age between 2020/21 and 2023, compared to 22.08% who reported a lower age in 2023. The highest share of increase was reported from the oldest age group (38.49%), compared to the middle-aged group (32.80%) and the youngest age group (24.66%).

Results of the fixed-effects interaction model are displayed in Table 5.

Table 5
Fixed-Effects Model Predicting Change in Planned Retirement Age, 2020/21-2023

	Change in planned retirement age
Job-related training (ref: 46-54 years)	
Yes	-0.16 (0.31)
Interaction Job-related training and age group	
Job-related training: Yes	0.55

	Change in planned retirement age
× Age group: 55-59 years	(0.33)
Job-related training: Yes	-0.20
× Age group: 60-65 years	(0.48)
<hr/>	
Income (ref: Low income)	
Medium income	-0.05 (0.20)
High income	-0.15 (0.35)
Occupational category (ref: High-skilled white-collar)	
Low-skilled white-collar	-0.68 (0.56)
High-skilled blue-collar	-0.75* (0.38)
Low-skilled blue-collar	-0.64* (0.26)
Sector (ref: Production sector)	
Private trade and service sector	0.89 (0.46)
Public sector	0.91* (0.43)
Working hours (ref: Full-time, ≥35h/week)	
Part-time (<35h/week)	-0.20 (0.36)
<hr/>	
Marital status (ref: Not married)	
Married	-0.91 (0.56)
Functional limitations (ref: No)	
Yes	-0.10 (0.25)
External health shock (ref: No)	
Yes	0.33 (0.24)
<hr/>	
Work-related stressors (ref: Not/hardly/a bit stressed)	
Physical demands	0.08 (0.22)
Environmental conditions	0.18 (0.20)
High workload	-0.37* (0.17)
New demands	-0.30 (0.25)
<hr/>	
Constant	64.98*** (0.63)

	Change in planned retirement age
Observations	1,408
Individuals	704
Within R ²	0.04
Individual FE	Yes

Note. Age groups are based on age in 2020/21. $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$

Participation in job-related training was not significantly associated with changes in planned retirement age among workers aged 46-54, the reference group ($b = -0.16$, $SE = 0.31$, $p = 0.617$). Furthermore, neither of the interaction terms reached levels of statistical significance, indicating that the association between training participation and planned retirement age did not differ significantly across age groups.

Regarding control variables, changes in occupation and sector appear to play a more consistent role: Transitions from high-skilled white-collar to high-skilled as well as to low-skilled blue-collar worker were associated with a decrease in planned retirement age and transitions from production sector into the public sector were associated with increases. Higher levels of work stress through a high workload was associated with a decrease in planned retirement age. Other time-varying factors were not significantly related to changes in planned retirement age.

Age-group-specific estimates derived from the interaction model indicated a positive association between training participation and planned retirement age among workers aged 55-59 years ($b = 0.39$, $SE = 0.16$, $p = 0.018$). To facilitate interpretation of the interaction model, Figure 1 presents age-group-specific marginal effects of training participation derived from the estimates shown in Table 5. This finding suggests that, although the interaction terms were not statistically significant, age-specific estimates suggested a positive association between training participation and an increased planned retirement age of approximately five months

among workers aged 55-59 years. No corresponding associations were observed among workers aged 46-54 ($b = -0.16$, $SE = 0.31$, $p = 0.617$) or 60-65 years ($b = -0.35$, $SE = 0.39$, $p = 0.363$). Thus, while interaction did not provide evidence for age differences, the pattern of estimates suggests that training participation may be particularly relevant during the transition phase immediately preceding retirement among workers aged 55-59 years.

Figure 1

Age-group-specific associations between job-related training participation and changes in planned retirement age, derived from the fixed-effects interaction model (2020/21-2023)

Note. Age groups are based on age in 2020/21. Points represent estimated age-group-specific associations of training participation. Vertical lines indicate 95% confidence intervals. Estimates are derived from the interaction model presented in Table 5.

Sensitivity Analyses

We conducted several sensitivity analyses to assess the robustness of the longitudinal fixed-effect results. First, as we did for the cross-sectional analyses, we replaced the dichotomous training variable with the measure of training frequency. Again, a positive association ($b = 0.69$, $SE = 0.23$, $p = 0.003$) between training and

changes in planned retirement age was observed among workers aged 55-59 who reported low levels of training participation (1-3 activities), but did not appear for workers aged 46-54 or workers aged 60-63. Higher training frequencies (4-10 activities / 11 and more activities) displayed lower coefficients that were not significantly related to changes in planned retirement age for neither age group. Second, we re-estimated the models after excluding workers who were self-employed in 2020/21 and/or in 2023. The overall pattern of results remained largely unchanged: There was no consistent main effect of training participation, while the positive association among workers aged 55-59 remained significant ($b = 0.34$, $SE = 0.17$, $p = 0.049$), indicating that the findings were not driven by the inclusion of self-employed individuals. Third, we defined age groups based on age in 2023 rather than age in 2020/21. In this specification, the previously observed positive association for workers aged 55-59 in 2020/21 became attenuated and no longer statistically significant.

Discussion

We examined whether participation in job-related training is associated with planned retirement age and with changes in planned retirement age over time. Our findings provide little evidence that job-related training is a universal predictor of (changes in) retirement planning. Cross-sectional associations were small and inconsistent across model specifications, while longitudinal analyses provided no evidence for a general within-person association. Moreover, neither the cross-sectional nor the longitudinal interaction terms indicated that these associations differed significantly across age groups. Nevertheless, age-specific estimates did suggest a positive association between training participation and changes in planned retirement age among workers aged 55-59 years. Taken together, our findings

indicate that the relationship between training participation and retirement planning is context-dependent and may vary across stages of the late career.

Job-related training participation is not a universal predictor of retirement planning

The absence of a consistent general association suggests that job-related training alone is unlikely to determine retirement planning. Cross-sectional associations were sensitive to model specifications, suggesting a rather small association, influenced by relationships among covariates and unmeasured confounding factors. Sensitivity analyses further confirmed the limited evidence for H1, as the association was not robust across sub-samples nor historical contexts. And while the 2020/21 analyses suggested a more positive association among workers aged 60-65, no comparable pattern was observed in 2017 or 2023, in contrast to hypothesis 1a which had suggested age-specific associations.

Previous research shows that training participation depends on many factors – Lischewski et al. (2020) identify strong institutional determinants on the participation in non-formal continuous vocational education and training, while Lössbroek & Radl (2019) emphasize the role of gender dynamics, and Turek & Henkens (2021) highlight path dependencies resulting from previous training participation. In addition, research suggests that retirement systems creating incentives for later retirement tend to be associated with higher training participation (Montizaan et al., 2009; Fouarge & Schils, 2009), suggesting that individuals planning to remain in the labor force longer may also be more likely to invest in training, making reverse causality a plausible explanation.

Job-related training participation is associated with increases in the planned retirement age for workers aged 55-59

Despite the absence of a general association in the longitudinal analyses, contradicting H2 and H2a, training participation was linked to increases in planned retirement among workers aged 55-59 years. This pattern is partly consistent with findings from the Netherlands by Stynen et al. (2016), who likewise report positive associations between development practices and continued working intentions for this age group. While the age pattern aligns with our results, their findings apply to combined development practices rather than training alone, suggesting that training may be less influential when considered in isolation. According to Feldman and Beehr (2011), retirement decisions evolve through several stages, from imagining retirement to developing concrete retirement plans. Workers in their late fifties may therefore be actively evaluating whether they remain capable of continuing employment, making training especially relevant. By contrast, retirement remains relatively distant for younger workers, whereas retirement plans among workers approaching retirement may already have become more firmly established and accompanied by work disengagement processes (Henning et al., 2023; 2026).

Theoretical implications

Whereas human capital theory assumes that investments in skills increase the expected returns to continued employment and therefore encourage longer working lives (Becker, 1964; Ben-Porath, 1967), we found no consistent association. Our findings suggest that additional human capital alone is insufficient to influence retirement planning. Instead, the findings suggest that the relevance of human capital for retirement planning depends on workers' career stage rather than operating

uniformly across the late career. Social exchange theory (Cropanzano & Mitchell, 2011) provides a complementary explanation: Participation in job-related training signals that employers continue to value and invest in older workers despite prevalent age stereotypes (Posthuma & Campion, 2009). Such investments may strengthen perceptions of organizational support and reciprocity, increasing the willingness to remain employed – but only while retirement decisions remain open to revision. Among younger older workers, for whom age-related stereotypes may be less pronounced, this mechanism may be less salient. Similarly, the Motivated Choice Framework suggests that training may increase or update person-organization fit, resulting in workers perceiving their work environment as more supportive – especially among older age groups (Kanfer et al., 2013) – and thereby encouraging continued employment during this specific decision phase.

The role of training frequency

Sensitivity analyses further suggested that positive associations were primarily driven by low frequencies of training participation (e.g., 1-3 activities), while higher training frequencies are not related to planned retirement age. The finding requires further research, particularly regarding the characteristics of the training itself, such as its intensity, content, or perceived relevance, rather than focusing solely on the number of training activities. Several mechanisms may explain our findings: One possibility is the selection into training, whereby workers experiencing difficulties may receive more trainings. Another explanation is that workers planning a career transition may participate more extensively in job-related training, while their reported planned retirement age may still reflect their current job situation rather than their anticipated future employment (Garthe & Hasselhorn, 2021).

Although the observed associations were modest, the findings suggest that training policies may be most effective when they target workers during the phase in which retirement decisions are actively formed rather than after retirement plans have largely crystallized. Rather than uniformly promoting training across the entire late career, employers may therefore benefit from tailoring development opportunities to workers' career stage.

Limitations

Several limitations should be considered when interpreting the findings. First, the analyses are observational and do not allow causal conclusions. While the longitudinal fixed-effects models account for stable unobserved individual characteristics, reverse causality remains possible, as individuals planning to work longer may be more likely to participate in training. Unobserved time-varying factors, such as changes in work performance, motivation, or employer support, could also influence both training participation and retirement planning.

Second, the measure of job-related training is relatively broad and does not capture important characteristics such as training content, duration, quality, or whether participation was initiated by the employer or the employee. Consequently, potentially relevant differences between types of training could not be examined.

Third, the longitudinal analyses are based on respondents who remained employed across both survey waves. As individuals who exited employment between 2020/21 and 2023 were not included, the analytical sample likely represents a relatively healthy and labor-market attached subgroup of older workers. The findings may therefore underestimate the importance of training among workers facing more

precarious employment situations or health-related barriers to continued employment.

Finally, retirement plans do not necessarily translate into actual retirement behavior. Although planned retirement age is a meaningful predictor of actual retirement timing, retirement trajectories may subsequently be influenced by unforeseen events such as health shocks, organizational changes, or family circumstances.

Conclusion

Job-related training is not a universal instrument for extending working lives, but it may influence retirement planning during a specific phase of the late career (i.e., workers aged 55-59), when retirement decisions become increasingly salient but remain open to revision (Feldman & Beehr, 2011). Our findings suggest that policies facilitating job-related training may contribute to later retirement planning among workers in their late fifties, although causal effects remain to be established. Future research should focus on underlying mechanisms and examine effects of different training characteristics.

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